

TRANSLATION PROCEDURES

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Annotation: *This article is interpreted on the basis of the issues of general linguistic description of translation procedures. It expresses features as the translation, strategies, sentences, range of perspectives and have been assigned a multitude of labels, among which we have procedures, techniques, strategies, processes and methods. the type of text, the purpose of the translation and the nature of the readers and words in translation of meaning on the logical basis of lexemes.*

Keywords: *fragmentation, homogeneous, translation procedure, comparative stylistics, systematic practice, translator's reach, empirical translator, manner of mistakes.*

INTRODUCTION

Within the field of theoretical translation, translation have been investigated from a wide range of perspectives and have been assigned a multitude of labels, among which we have procedures, techniques, strategies, processes and methods. the type of text, the purpose of the translation and the nature of the readers. The confusing use of terminology and concepts has encouraged the fragmentation of a branch of translation research that proves to be more homogeneous than may appear at first sight.

One of the first names given to these translation process operators was 'translation procedure' (English translation for *proce'de' technique de la traduction*), a term coined by Vinay and Darbelnet in 1958. Unanimously acclaimed as the main proponents of comparative stylistics applied to translation, Vinay and Darbelnet understand the term 'translation procedure' as all those processes that come into play when shifting between two languages.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The procedure is linguistic tools to facilitate the work of the translator: "Only systematic practice can provide translators with mastery over these procedures with which they can achieve certainty, ease and speed. Without the knowledge of these techniques which contemporary linguistics have put within the translator's reach, the empirical translator will continue to be embroiled in continued puzzles which will take up precious time and, most important of all, s/he will be condemned to using literalisms which are the universal cause of all manner of mistakes".

There is the distinction between 'stylistic technique procedures' and 'general translation procedures'. While the first term includes two fundamental types of translation (literal translation; oblique or dynamic translation), the second

encompasses the preparation of the translation project and its revision. From a conceptual and methodological point, this distinction opens the way to a new, more complex and heterogeneous understanding of the study of the translation process.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The terms 'strategy', 'rule' and 'procedure' are used with the same meaning as 'translation techniques'. The association of terms such as 'rule', 'norm', 'law', 'standard', etc., with terms such as 'procedures', 'techniques', 'strategies', etc., has been and continues to be a common feature in translation studies. But perhaps what is of particular interest here is the introduction of the communicative aspect as a fundamental element in the translation process.

The end purpose of both translation and interpreting, which are under the general heading of transfer consists of producing for a given source language text a communicatively equivalent text in the target language. Vinay and Darbelnet's were the first who gave classification of translation techniques that had a clear methodological purpose. They defined seven basic procedures operating on three levels of style: lexis, distribution (morphology and syntax) and message. The procedures were classified as direct (or literal) or oblique, to coincide with their distinction between direct (or literal) and oblique translation. Literal translation occurs when there is an exact structural, lexical, even morphological equivalence between two languages.

CONCLUSION

According to the translation theorists, this is only possible when the two languages are very close to each other. The direct translation procedures are:

- **Borrowing.** A word from the source text is directly transferred to the target, that is, a word is taken directly from another language and employed with its same form in the TT without translation. This technique is used in English and other languages in order to fill a semantic gap in the TT. This procedure is applied by borrowing a word or expression in the source language to overcome an unknown concept in the culture of the target language. Borrowing is applied to introduce the flavor of the source language culture. The decision to borrow source language word or expression to introduce an element of source language is a matter of style, however, it may have significant effects on the message contained.

- **Calque.** A foreign word or phrase translated and incorporated into another language. This is "a special kind of borrowing", according to Vinay and Darbelnet⁵², where the SL phrase or expression is literally translated word-for-word. Besides, they add that borrowings and calques are sometimes fully accompanied into the TL, although they suffer sometimes some semantic changes, which can turn them into false friends. Calques contribute to the richness of the translation in the TL by avoiding the direct use of foreign words. It is noteworthy that some authors use the concept of "loan translation" as a synonym for calque. However, a calque is a construction, where a word or phrase is borrowed from another language while translating its components

in order to create a new lexeme in the TL, respecting the syntactical structures of the SL, while a loan may be a phonetic and morphological adaptation.

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